

THE BENEFITS OF READING PHILOSOPHICAL LITERATURE BOOKS TO IMPROVE WORLDVIEW IN LEARNING LANGUAGES

Shahnozabegim Yokubjonova

Student of Samarkand State institute of foreign languages, young

researcher from Samarkand, Uzbekistan;

shahnozabegimyoqubjonova@gmail.com

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Abstract.

As it can be seen by the name of the article, this research paper intends to discuss the ways in which reading philosophical books can help with broadening languages learners horizons and open up their minds to the world and new ideas. Also, I aim to list the major advantages of reading such books as a habit. This article is mainly based on the personal views of the author.

Key words: philosophy, critical thinking, logical thinking, analytical skills, problem solving, mastering one's profession;

INTRODUCTION

As one lives in this world, no matter how much they try it is evident and apparent that one day they are probably going to face with difficulties, hardships or even with shortcomings. This is the eternal truth in this temporary world. However, as a young growing up girl and researcher of life and my own profession, I believe and think that reading books regularly is something that gives me wings when I am in a bottom of the room. "We all want to feel proud of ourselves. To gain a sense of ultimate purpose. To feel we are living a good life the right way and, perhaps, through living well, find some way to answer that niggling question: "Why Bother?" To act morally, and with conviction, is to gain a sense of purpose, self-respect and fulfillment." (John McCone, 2018); So, after experiencing a lot of occasions in my life, I decided to wrote this paper work to describe the value of reading books especially philosophical ones. This article will mention the reasons why I think that philosophical literature will help to learn the language faster and list the benefits of it.

1.0 Why Philosophical Books Help People Learn Languages Faster?

I profoundly believe that there are numerous reasons for this. First of all, philosophy is something that people come up with experiencing, suffering and understanding something in life. And apparently, for generations there are still some universal truth which looks like to remain permanent throughout the entire human race. So, the first reason why reading such books will help is because it has the ability to convey this strong messages to people mainly to the

young generations, making it easy to understand and realize without experiencing on themselves. “Academic Philosophers spend lifetimes analyzing just one idea or one writer. These academics refine/clarify their arguments and/or place a certain thinker’s thoughts as a lens over how to view our current society.” (Fresh, 2022);

Also, these universal beliefs make people to think for a long period of time even about one statement. Due to this, people will develop problem solving, critical and analytical thinking abilities unconsciously in the long journey. “I noticed that philosophy books like The Republic, Ethics, The Prince, and The Clash of Civilizations are on the top of required readings for Ivy League students.” (Fresh, 2022);

One more thing which makes learning beautiful is that learners really enjoy reading these books as they really take close the things they are reading to themselves. According to scientists, people mostly like to read about life, people experiences and such stuff rather than reading boring articles about unknown things. Thus, it is really good thing to practice reading philosophical literature during the language learning journey. They easily sharpen their life skills by doing so as mentioned above.

2.0 Benefits That Comes With Reading Philosophical Literature

As you can see I have counted some benefits above. But still there are a lot of known and unknown benefits behind reading. Some may sound surprising while some do not to the reader. The best way to check these benefits is of course by practice and reading in the real time. In short, here is a list of things it can improve which also helps to improve the language learning process as well worldview:

- Logical thinking,;
- Analyzing & problem solving skills,;
- Assessing possible solutions;
- The ability to write and speak clearly, attending to details.

“Students learn about questions. How to ask good questions and distinguish the worthwhile from the worthless questions. How to divide, prioritize, and simplify questions” (Castleton University, 2022); An observe of philosophy will assist you expand crucial questioning skills. It will inspire you to recognize the restrictions you use inside while you make sure picks or maybe whilst making a decision which desires you ought to pursue. You might be capable of assume intelligently of ways you stay and why you stay that way. Concepts like correlation and causation turns into clearer and you’ll be capable of make higher deductions and inferences.

Well, these are the things that almost everyone is very fond of having in language learning process. Of course, all of them comes with time and practice. The more the reader reads and reflects upon certain circumstances, the reader will start getting the Ice berg meaning and will make his/her own conclusions.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, although the benefits do not come overnight, reading philosophical books is actually an excellent way to boost not only language learning process, but also one's mind and views, opinions, thoughts about the world and surrounding. As a result, one will have a number of skills that a person needs in this day and age.

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